

THROUGH-THICKNESS CURE MONITORING OF THICK ADVANCED COMPOSITES USING DIELECTRIC SENSORS

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SUMMARY

In this study, resin transfer moulding is used to fabricate thick composite flat panels. Since manufacturing of thick panels is accompanied with many processing problems due to the exothermic reaction of the resin system, dielectric sensors are embedded to measure the effect of the exothermic reaction on the through-thickness progress of the curing state.

Keywords: resin transfer moulding (RTM), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), dielectric sensors, through-thickness cure monitoring, thick-walled advanced composites

INTRODUCTION

Since the last decades, several techniques have been developed for manufacturing of advanced composites. One of these techniques is Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM). Although LCM techniques such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) and vacuum infusion can be used to manufacture complicated structures with high-quality standards, these are often thin-walled. Or, if an increased thickness is needed (e.g., for stiffening aircraft flooring) a sandwich-like structure consisting of fibre reinforced skins and a foam core is used. Contrary to the relative easiness of manufacturing high-quality thin-walled structures, thick-walled composite structures (i.e., structures with a thickness larger than ten millimetres) induce difficulty on the fabrication process. One of the main sources to these problems comes from the exothermic reaction of the polymer. With an increased ratio of volume to surface and low thermal conductivities of both fibres and resin, the released heat during the exothermic reaction can hardly diffuse away. As a consequence, the reaction temperature will increase and thermal gradients may appear leading to increased residual stresses and/or structural defects. Applying a mould temperature profile as defined by the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle (MRCC) can lead to excessive cure inside the part. This could cause non-uniform degree of cure

through the thickness and therefore residual stress and/or structural defects. The problems in curing of thick-walled composites emphasise the necessity of a better understanding of the different phenomena occurring in the curing process of polymers [1].

In this study, a combination of Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) tests and dielectric ion conductivity measurements were used to relate the output of embedded and tool-mounted dielectric sensors to the cure state of a high-performance resin system in-situ during the manufacturing of thick composite panels. Furthermore, models were established for the glass transition temperature and cure kinetics. It should be noted that the final goal of this study is to optimise the cure cycle for thick composites and predict through-thickness degree of cure and glass transition temperature.

THEORY

The theory was already described in Ref. 2, but for the sake of completeness it is briefly outlined below. Since thermosetting resins belong to the group of dielectric materials due to dipoles existing in functional groups of the molecules as well as by the ions present in the resins, they have capacitive and conductive properties. The dielectric response of the resins is thus mainly caused by the dipole orientation and ion migration. Based on these properties, the complex permittivity is given as:

$$\varepsilon^* = \varepsilon' - i\varepsilon'' \quad (1)$$

where ε' is the dielectric constant or relative permittivity and ε'' is the dielectric loss factor. The former is mainly associated with dipole orientation, whereas the latter is a measure of the total energy lost in the dielectric material caused by both dipole relaxation and ion migration. According to Ref. 3, the dielectric loss factor equals:

$$\varepsilon'' = \frac{(\varepsilon_r + \varepsilon_u)\omega\tau}{1 + \omega^2\tau^2} + \frac{\sigma}{\omega\varepsilon_0} \quad (2)$$

where ε_u is the unrelaxed permittivity, ε_r is the relaxed permittivity, τ is the relaxation time, ω is the angular frequency, σ is the ionic conductivity, and ε_0 is the permittivity of the free space. In Ref. 3 it was mentioned that the contribution of the dipole orientation to the dielectric loss is negligible at low frequencies. When this observation is taken into account, Eq. (2) can be rewritten as:

$$\varepsilon'' = \frac{\sigma}{\omega\varepsilon_0} = \frac{\sigma}{2\pi f\varepsilon_0} \quad (3)$$

in which f is introduced as being the test frequency. A change in viscosity of the thermosetting resins affects the mobility of the ions and consequently also the ionic conductivity. Thus measuring the change in ionic conductivity gives information about the arrival of the resin flow front at the sensor's position and can also be used for

following the cure state of composites. For the latter, the ionic conductivity has to be correlated with the glass transition temperature, T_g , and degree of conversion, α . The following correlation function is proposed by Refs. 4 and 5:

$$\frac{\log \sigma}{\log \sigma_0} = \phi + \phi T_g \quad (4)$$

where σ_0 is the initial ion conductivity (i.e., before the start of the curing reaction), ϕ and ϕ are material parameters.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Materials

In this study, a newly developed resin system supplied by Hexcel was used: the bi-component RTM 6 resin system. Because of transport restrictions of the monocomponent equivalent, Hexcel developed this two-part resin system. It has the same Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC): preheat the resin to 80°C, preheat the mould to 120°C, inject the resin and cure at 160°C for 75 minutes followed by a postcure of 120 minutes at 180°C. Moreover, after mixing it should have similar characteristics as the monocomponent RTM 6 resin system. These include storage conditions. The fibrous reinforcement consisted of multiple layers of an 8 harness satin weave glass fabric (HexForce® 7581 supplied by Hexcel).

DSC Measurements

The cure kinetics of the bi-component RTM 6 resin system was investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Q1000, TA Instruments). Ten samples of uncured resin, weighing about 10mg, were tested in the dynamic scanning mode at the following heating rates: 2, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, and 20°C/min, in order to determine the total heat of reaction. Subsequently, a series of samples of uncured resin were isothermally cured at four different temperatures: 140°C, 151°C, 160°C, and 180°C for different time periods. To reach the isothermal temperature a heating rate of 100°C/min was chosen. The cooling after the isothermal period was done at a rate of 30°C/min, which should be fast enough to 'freeze' the reaction instantaneously. After this, the samples were dynamically scanned at a heating rate of 10°C/min to determine both the residual heat of reaction and the glass transition temperature. The fractional conversion of the partially cured samples was obtained by comparing the residual heat of reaction with the total heat of reaction.

In the experiment, some additional isothermal curing scenarios were tested by using modulated differential scanning calorimetry (MDSC, 2920, TA Instruments) at the following temperatures: 140°C, 150°C, 160°C, 170°C, and 180°C. The heating rate was set to 25°C/min. The heat flow was measured during the isothermal cure and, subsequently, converted to the reaction rate. Integration of the reaction rate with respect to time yields the degree of conversion.

Dielectric Measurements

Two different types of dielectric sensors were involved in this study: a tool-mounted sensor and filtered IDEX sensors with 14 inch leads. The tool-mounted sensor had two planar interdigitated comb electrodes placed on a flat ceramic substrate. The filtered IDEX sensors were used for embedding between layers of the fabric and had a filter made of glass woven fabric to prevent contact with electrical conductive materials. Both sensors were connected to a 10-channels dielectric sensor system, DEA 230/10, from NETZSCH Instruments. Since the tool-mounted sensor was already integrated in the upper part of a modular RTM mould, samples of about 10g were cured on the mould surface of this upper part and at different isothermal temperatures (140°C, 151°C, 160°C, and 180°C) for about five hours, while the test frequency of the dielectric sensor was set to 1Hz. Also for the filtered IDEX sensors, the upper mould part was used as the mould surface for curing resin samples, in which a single filtered IDEX sensor was embedded. Experiments were performed at the same isothermal temperatures.

Online Cure Monitoring in RTM Process for Thick-Walled Composites

Up to now a single experiment has been performed. Between two matched mould parts made of steel tool and inside a picture-frame made of aluminium tubing and rubber sheets, a 10mm thick panel (200mm x 250mm) was manufactured. A total of 50 layers of the glass woven fabric were stacked ($[0/90]_{50}$) resulting in a fibre volume fraction of about 57%. Three dielectric sensors and five J-type thermocouples were used to monitor the through-thickness curing of the thermosetting resin. The tool-mounted dielectric sensor measured the ionic conductivity at the top of the plate, whereas the two filtered IDEX sensors were embedded between the lower mould part and first layer and between the 25th and 26th layers. The thermocouples were embedded between lower mould part and first layer, between 10th and 11th layers, between 25th and 26th layers, between 40th and 41st layers, and 50th layer and upper mould part. All sensors were located in the centre of the preform. The preform was impregnated using a line injection strategy. After fully impregnation the resin was cured according to the mould temperature profile shown in Fig. 1. It should be noted that the first dwell period (at 118°C) corresponds to the injection period. Heating was performed by electrical resistance, whereas the mould was cooled down with the aid of a ventilator.

Figure 1: Mould temperature profile

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Correlation between Dielectric and DSC Experiments

From the DSC experiments, the glass transition temperature and the degree of conversion were obtained by post-processing the heat flow curves. First of all, the curves from the specimens tested in dynamic scanning mode were integrated to find the total heat of reaction, H_u . In Table 1 the total heat that was released for each heating rate is given. By taking the average, a mean value was found of 429.6 J/g with a standard deviation of 18.27 J/g. From the experiments performed at different isothermal temperatures and for predefined cure periods, the residual heat of reaction and the glass transition temperature were determined. The results are shown in Figs. 1a and 1b (the measurement points are represented by symbols).

Simultaneously with the DSC experiments (performed at NRC), a series of experiments were performed at the Delft University of Technology. After data processing, curves for the degree of conversion versus time were found (solid lines in Fig. 1b). It should be noted that for these curves the total heat of reaction was slightly different (390.2 J/g instead of 429.6 J/g). Nevertheless, the curves showed good similarity with the data points collected from the DSC experiments. The final degree of conversion was comparable for each isothermal cure condition and also the evolution of the cure state coincided with the data points at higher isothermal temperatures. Only at low isothermal conditions (140°C and 150°C) the cure evolution deviated. A possible explanation could be the differences in heating rates such that the starting point of the time scales may not be correctly defined. Furthermore, because of the use of two DSC instruments, there could be differences between the outputs and a closer look is needed on the interchangeability of the experimental data from different instruments.

To correlate the glass transition temperature and degree of conversion to the log ion conductivity, the change in log ion conductivity due to the curing of the thermosetting resin was monitored at different isothermal temperatures using the two types of dielectric sensors. Figure 3a shows the evolution of the log ion conductivity as measured with the tool-mounted sensor, whereas Fig. 3b displays the results for the filtered IDEX sensor. Both sensors recorded comparable curing behaviour for the samples cured at the highest two isothermal temperatures (160°C and 180°C). More striking is the difference between the outputs at the lowest two isothermal temperatures.

Whereas the filtered IDEX sensor showed a steady decrease in log ion conductivity up to stabilisation (the indication that the resin had reached its final cure state for that isothermal cure temperature), the tool-mounted sensor recorded a sudden change in the log ion conductivity at around 75 minutes. Initially, there was a linear decrease in log ion conductivity. But after 75 minutes, the decline in log ion conductivity became faster until it reaches a certain stabilisation value. Although the experiments were performed correctly, the correlation between the log ion conductivity and the glass transition temperature (Eq. 4) has not been completed yet. More dielectric experiments have to be performed in order to find a proper fit.

Table 1: Overview of total heat of reaction for each heating rate

Heating rate [°C/min]	2	4	5	6	8	10	12	15	18	20	Mean	Standard Deviation
Total heat of reaction [J/g]	447.5	451.9	409.1	411.4	424.6	409.2	454.5	450.9	420.9	416.3	429.6	18.27

Figure 2: DSC experiments - (a) glass transition temperature versus degree of conversion, (b) degree of conversion versus time

Figure 3: Dielectric ion conductivity - (a) tool-mounted sensor, (b) filtered IDEX sensor

Online Monitoring of the Curing Process of a Thick Composite Plate

After preforming, sensor placing, and mould closing, the mould was heated to a temperature of about 120°C. Meanwhile the resin was preheated to 80°C. As soon as the heating of the mould stabilised at the set temperature data recording was started. Minutes later the injection was started. When the resin reached the vent and with the assumption that the preform was fully impregnated by this time, the inlet was closed. The cure cycle was continued by following the two-step cure cycle shown in Fig. 1. Figure 4 shows the results of the data recordings. In Fig. 4a the log ion conductivity is plotted versus time. The step change at 22 minutes was due to the arrival of the resin at the sensors. Furthermore, although the initial values after resin arrival were different for the tool-mounted and filtered IDEX sensor, the shape of the curves were comparable indicating probably that the conditions at the mould surface were similar on both sides of the laminate's thickness. A clear difference existed between the IDEX sensor embedded in the middle of the laminate and the filtered IDEX sensor at the bottom side. After resin arrival, both sensors recorded the same log ion conductivity, but the one in

Figure 4: Experimental data recorded during the curing process - (a) log ion conductivity versus time, (b) through-thickness instantaneous cure temperature (zoomed in on curing period)

the middle decreased to a much lower value during the cure dwell period (between 55 minutes and 130 minutes). Figure 4b shows the through-thickness temperature distribution during this dwell period. It can be seen that in the middle of the laminate a slightly higher temperature was measured (up to 2°C difference with the mould surface). This observation may explain the differences in dielectric measurements: a higher cure temperature resulted in a faster reaction and also a higher final degree of conversion (Fig. 2b). Since the correlation has not been completed yet, a solid conclusion is therefore not possible. Furthermore, it has to be mentioned that the IDEX sensor in the middle of the laminate was not covered with a glass filter.

Modelling the Cure Kinetics

Although material characterisation is still ongoing, the first results with respect to simulation of the curing process are briefly described below. First of all, the increasing glass transition temperature with increasing degree of conversion (Fig. 2a) is modelled with the well-known and often applied DiBenedetto equation (see, for example, Ref. 6 and 7). That is,

$$T_g = T_{g0} + \frac{(T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})\lambda\alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha} \quad (5)$$

where T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$ are the glass transition temperatures of the uncured and fully-cured resin, and λ is a material parameter. Table 2 shows the parameters for the fitted curve that is represented by the dashed line in Fig. 2a.

To model the cure kinetics of the bi-component RTM 6 resin system a three-step modelling strategy was adopted. First, the vitrification point was determined by plotting the $\ln(d\alpha/dt)$ versus time plot based on the DSC results performed at the Delft

University of Technology. The vitrification point splits the reaction into a chemically-controlled region (cure temperature higher than the instantaneous glass transition temperature) and a diffusion-controlled region (cure temperature lower than the instantaneous glass transition temperature). Subsequently, a cure kinetics model was fitted to the experimental data of the chemically-controlled region.

The same model (without diffusion-limited rate constant) as in Ref. 1 was used for characterisation of the cure kinetics:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2\alpha^m)(1-\alpha)^n \quad (6)$$

where the reaction-limited kinetic rate constants were defined as:

$$k_i = A_i \exp\left(\frac{-E_i}{RT}\right) \quad \text{for } i=1,2 \quad (7)$$

In these equations, E is the activation energy, A is a rate constant, m and n are reaction orders, and R is the universal gas constant. Based on minimisation of the sum of squared error the best fit obtained is shown in Fig. 5. The estimated parameters are listed in Table 3. Since the diffusion-controlled region was not taken into account, the model predicted a full cure at each isothermal temperature. The third step is to include the diffusion-controlled region in the model. However, this has not been considered yet because of time restrictions.

Table 2: Fitting parameters for T_g (Eq. 5)

Parameter	T_{g0} [°C]	$T_{g\infty}$ [°C]	λ [-]
Value	-14.58	220.51	0.383

Figure 5: Modelling the cure kinetics of the bi-component RTM 6 resin system - (a) reaction rate versus time, (b) degree of conversion versus time

Table 3: Estimated parameters for cure kinetics model (Eqs. 6-7)

Parameter	A_1	E_1	A_2	E_2	m	n	R
	10^3 [1/s]	[kJ/mol]	10^3 [1/s]	[kJ/mol]	[-]	[-]	[J/(mol-K)]
Value	44.62	74.41	17.65	58.16	1.171	1.114	8.314

CONCLUSION

By manufacturing a 10mm thick glass fibre reinforced RTM 6 panel that was monitored online and in-situ by dielectric sensors and thermocouples, the injection and curing were followed for a thick-walled composite panel made by the RTM process. The flow-front was detected at the sensors' locations and the cure state was monitored throughout the curing process. Differences were observed between the sensors embedded in the middle of the laminate and at the mould surface. The exothermic reaction caused in the middle a temperature increase of 2°C compared to the mould temperature. Nevertheless, the correlation between degree of conversion and glass transition temperature and log ion conductivity was not completed and therefore it is too early to form a solid conclusion.

Furthermore, for simulation purposes the glass transition temperature was modelled with the so-called DiBenedetto equation. The chemically-controlled region of the cure kinetics was also fitted to a model.

FUTURE WORK

Obviously, one part of the future work will consider the correlation of the experimental data. Moreover, to gain more insight into the curing process of thick-walled composites more panels of different thicknesses have to be manufactured. The modelling of the material parameters will also be continued in order to set up a simulation model of the curing process of thick-walled composites.

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